

WELCOME TO
Semiannual GreenX3 Newsletter

In this newsletter you will find:

- DCs/DNSs Project Objectives & Actions
- GreenX3 Project Training Activities
- Past and Upcoming Events

Enjoy Reading!

In our second GreenX3 newsletter

GreenX3 – a Marie Skłodowska-Curie Doctoral program is offering a unique platform to 13 Doctoral Candidates/Doctoral Networks Students (DCs/DNSs) from multidisciplinary research backgrounds shape a sustainable future.

GreenX3 consortium is paying great attention to professional career development of researchers via different activities. Firstly, Training on Team Building & Soft Skills was organized for the DCs/DNSs in June 2024 at MyBiotech GmbH, Uberherrn, Germany.

Moreover, DCs/DNSs had an opportunity to express themselves along with their project progress and academic background to consortium in 1st international meeting, Review meeting, and 1st Summer school in September 2024 organized by University of Trieste, Trieste, Italy.

[GreenX3](#)

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Hello everyone, greetings from MyBiotech GmbH in the beautiful town of Überherrn!
Since starting my project here, so much has happened, and I'm excited to share highlights with you on this page.

We had the pleasure of hosting all DCs and DNSs right here in Überherrn for our very first meeting.

It was such an exciting experience to meet everyone in person for the first time. I was genuinely energized by the positivity we shared.

Then, we reunited in the beautiful city of Trieste for our international meeting and summer school, which was a perfect chance to share projects,

explore collaborations and connect with supervisors and partners. After spending such meaningful days together in Trieste, saying goodbye was bittersweet—I'm already missing all of you!

A Little Bit About My Project: Transforming Byproducts into Resources

Unlike the traditional 'take, make, dispose' linear model that consumes resources and creates waste, the circular economy focuses on reducing waste and maximizing the use of materials. This transition benefits both the environment and the economy.

*Taken and modified from:
<https://www.nofreelunch.co.uk/>

As we face growing environmental challenges, more industries are adopting the "circular economy approach". Instead of simply throwing things away, this model encourages reusing and recycling materials to get the most value from them, inspiring us all to use resources wisely and minimize waste wherever possible.

This approach not only helps protect our environment but also paves the way for a sustainable future for everyone.

One of the key elements of the circular economy is viewing waste as a potential resource. My project brings this idea to life by applying industrial symbiosis: *the waste from one industry becomes the raw material for another*. In GreenX3, we aim to transform fish oil waste—a byproduct often discarded after Omega-3 production—into valuable products like cholesterol and Vitamin D3. By giving new life to materials that would otherwise go unused, we reflect the "waste-to-value" philosophy of the circular economy approach. This innovative solution not only reduces waste but also creates new benefits for the pharmaceutical industry.

As more industries adopt these sustainable practices, my work on GreenX3 offers an exciting opportunity to highlight the potential of "waste-to-value" processes at MyBiotech GmbH. My hope is that our efforts will serve as a positive example for the future, inspiring others to make sustainable development a priority.

Shehneela JAMIL

My participation

After making a *home* in current hometown, I had the opportunity to meet all the DCs/DNSs in Saarlouis for the first time in June. All of them coming from different parts of the world, each bringing a unique set of skills and perspectives. This diversity made the experience incredibly enriching. Moreover, engaging activities and games planned by organizing team at MyBiotech GmbH in training sessions helped us bond. This first meeting felt more like a *team* coming together.

Then, in Trieste, to participate in 1st international meeting & summer school, I got the chance to meet everyone from the consortium including the researchers and advisors. This time, I truly grasped the deeper idea of GreenX3 project when all of us presented our side of research work in this consortium.

Moreover, Trieste itself was the perfect setting for such an event in September. After our scientific sessions, I had the chance to catch the sun & moon in colorful evening skies of Trieste. Visiting the castle, relaxing at the beach, and strolling through the city was a great way to recharge and connect with the team outside of the usual work setting.

Understanding My Work

Participating in the GreenX3 project as Doctoral Candidate 2 (DC2) has offered me a unique opportunity to deepen my scientific and practical knowledge. My project focuses on improving the bioavailability, solubility, and stability issues of lipophilic active pharmaceutical ingredients (APIs). Scientifically, APIs are the components that provide therapeutic effects, but many of these compounds—especially those classified under the Biopharmaceutics Classification System (BCS) Class II & IV—are lipophilic, meaning they don't like water. This intrinsic character limits their solubility and absorption in the body, reducing their therapeutic effectiveness.

No matter how hard we try, we can't **dissolve** our differences

Let's **emulsify** their differences!!

This challenging aspect take scientists on an adventure of defining and customizing drug delivery systems that can protect and deliver these lipophilic APIs efficiently in our body. Following this, I as DC2, am focusing on creating green and scalable methods for encapsulating these APIs, which not only enhances their stability and solubility but also aligns with green chemistry principles. I aim to create straightforward, environmentally friendly processes that can be applied to various manufacturing platforms. Therefore, I am contributing to development of green manufacturing protocols to deliver APIs using innovative technologies and methods.

Secondees at MyBiotech GmbH

In October, we welcomed Saad as a secondee at MyBiotech GmbH. In case you're wondering, a "secondee" is one of the project's DC/DNS who joins another partner institute to collaborate and contribute to their research project.

As DC2, I had the opportunity to help create a welcoming environment for Saad (DC4), and it was a valuable learning experience for me.

This month, Elisa (DC3) also joined us for her secondment.

Now, all four of us DCs from the GreenX3 project are wrapping up 2024 together at MyBiotech GmbH.

GreenX3-DC3

Supervisor: Prof. Rolf Müller
HIPS/UdS/MyBiotech - Germany

Elisa de Lannoy
Guerra

Hi! I am Elisa, a chemist from Brazil and the DC3! During my master I studied in France, Germany and Poland. Professional wise, my interests are metabolomics, natural products, NMR and organic spectrometric techniques. By applying those interests to the pharmaceutical/biotechnology field, I hope to contribute for a healthier planet.

Currently, I am a MSCA doctoral candidate at Universität des Saarlandes / Helmholtz Institute for Pharmaceutical Research Saarland (HIPS) with secondment at MyBiotech GmbH.

Würzburg
(DE)

- Symposium/poster
- Käsespätzle

VAAM Symposium

I also had the chance to do a short business trip to Würzburg (DE) with some colleagues from HIPS lab. It was our first time presenting our projects in a natural products symposium, as a poster (in my case) or as a short talk. This was an important step for us - first- and second-year doctoral candidates. By preparing and participating on academic events, step by step we acquire new skills for disseminating science.

In my opinion, those scientific but also social gatherings play an outstanding role when it comes to enhancing work environment and motivation. Not mentioning the network strengthening. The Symposium and the Summer School were for sure some of the highlights of my second PhD semester.

Trieste
(IT)

- James Joyce
- Pizza Bianca
- Synchrotron

1st GreenX3 Summer School

Summer School at Trieste was super important for our feeling of belonging. This group feeling was ignited in June, at Überherrn - DE, with our first „Tête-à-Tête“ training, and it got strengthened at Trieste, as we had more time to be together. It was also nice to have some time with my supervisor and having the opportunity to meet the other P.I.s.

Besides getting some rainy and windy nights, I was lucky to have good weather in the first day and being able to dive into Trieste's lovely sea! This definitely helped to come back full of energy to work in our project.

Project updates

Now my projects got a more defined design and hands on!

Project 1: New bacteria – exciting! Will we find a new compound? Bioactive? Keep following the newsletter to discover it with me!

Project 2: Does supercritical fluid-based chromatography enable new features to be discovered? Let's discover that by metabolomics data analysis comparing chromatograms from myxobacteria extracts injected in UPC²-MS and TIMSTOF-MS. Keep following the news and get to know in which cases UPC²-MS points out new features!

This week my secondment started. And I am having a flashback to my working times at the industry. Here, at MyBiotech GmbH, I will look for enhancing myxobacteria extraction methods with the assistance of the MJR and scaling up the new bacteria strain from project 1!

GreenX3 - DC4

Saad Ur Rehman who I am?

I am a Pharmacist from Pakistan. I completed Pharm-D from the University of Karachi and started my professional career as a formulation scientist in the pharmaceutical industry in Pakistan. I did the Erasmus Mundus Joint Master's Degree (EMJMD), in Nanomedicine for Drug Delivery from the University of Paris, University of Angers, University of Pavia, and University of Patras in France, Italy and Greece.

I have a passion to work on the development of an innovative solution to prepare nanoparticles to load therapeutic molecules and improve pharmaceutical formulations. Following this passion, I joined GreenX3 Project as a MSCA doctoral Candidate at the Universität des Saarlandes with secondment at MyBiotech.

GreenX3 group, doctoral candidates and supervisors at University of Trieste. September 2024.

Starting of secondment at Mybiotech, Überherrn. October, 2024.

Supervisor: Prof. Dr. Marc Schneider, Dr Nazende Günday Türeli
University of Saarland, Saarbrücken, Germany

Experience in GreenX3 Project

GreenX3 project has provided me with the lot of opportunity to get trained on new and green techniques of preparing nanoparticles for drug delivery system. So far, in almost 8 months, with the help of my supervisor, I have been working on several new equipment and lab techniques for preparation and characterization of nanoparticles. I believe that pharmaceutical industry requires sustainable and innovative processes to be able to overcome current problem of increasing carbon content in the environment. I am very happy and excited that by joining this program, I am contributing towards the advancement of pharmaceutical formulations and betterment of the environment.

Our first international training held at MyBiotech GmbH in Überherrn, Germany was a very enriching experience. We had the chance to meet all the doctoral candidates from all around the Europe. It was a very useful and important training on transferrable skills organized by MyBiotech. I learnt a lot about a better way to tackle problems and hurdles that we might face during this PhD tenure.

We had a great experience in our first international meeting and summer school held at University of Trieste in Trieste, Italy. We had a chance to present our scientific progress in international meeting, where we received feedback about our progress and several useful recommendations from the experts in the field. We also got a chance to present our background, education and experience to everyone. In summer school we received training about several critical topics related to our PhD journey.

GreenX3 group, doctoral candidates in Mybiotech, Überherrn. June 2024.

Prof. Dr. Marc Schneider's lab group at Universität des Saarlandes, Saarbrücken. May 2024.

Secondment at MyBiotech GmbH

From October 2024, I have already started my secondment at MyBiotech GmbH, which is a pharmaceutical industry. First, it is a very nice experience to work in both settings i.e., Academic and Industrial environment. I believe that this opportunity will help me a lot in career in future. Here in MyBiotech GmbH, I am being trained to work in industrial settings, which strictly follows GMP (Good Manufacturing Practices) regulations. I have been planning to work on preparing drug delivery system using the same manufacturing process I used in Universität des Saarlandes to improve bioavailability of certain drugs. Better bioavailability would mean better effectiveness of a drug for the patient and greener and sustainable pharmaceutical formulation.

In MyBiotech, I was welcomed warm-heartedly by MyBiotech team. I also have an opportunity to work along with other DCs. It is a very nice working environment, where we can help each other as well. I am very much looking forward to 18 months of my secondment in MyBiotech GmbH.

Marta Vinha Vieira

Olá!

I am a pharmacist and food technologist, originally from the beautiful island of Florianópolis, Brazil. I am currently pursuing an industrial doctorate as an MSCA Fellow at Nanomol Technologies and ICMAB-CSIC in Barcelona, under the framework of the GreenX3 project.

Curiosity has always driven me, guiding both my academic pursuits and personal adventures. I have been fortunate to experience life in various countries, each offering unique experiences. In my free time, I enjoy outdoor activities, travelling, reading, and spending quality time with loved ones.

GreenX3 fellows- MyBiotech, Überrhern (Germany)

1st Summer School, Trieste (Italy)

Gelato time! GreenX3 group, Trieste (Italy)

#7

What is my project about?

Developing effective medications is both complex and costly, with traditional methods like pills and injections often require frequent dosing and cause side effects. To address these challenges, the pharmaceutical industry is advancing innovative drug delivery systems, such as nanocarriers and hydrogels, designed to improve patient compliance, minimise side effects, and enable controlled drug release.

Within the GreenX3 framework, my project focuses on sustainable pharmaceutical nanoformulations developed using low-emission, green technologies. At its core is the development of DELOS nanovesicles—nanoscale lipid vesicles manufactured through a patented eco-friendly process by Nanomol Technologies and ICMAB-CSIC. These stable, biocompatible particles can carry both water- and fat-soluble drugs, making them highly versatile for diverse biomedical applications.

As the ultimate goal, we aim to explore DELOS nanovesicles-based formulations for oral and subcutaneous drug delivery. For oral administration, we seek to overcome digestive barriers by improving drug stability and bioavailability. While for subcutaneous delivery, we focus on creating a gel-like depot that provides extended drug release, ensuring consistent therapeutic levels and reducing the dosing frequency, which is particularly advantageous for treating long-term conditions. Through these initiatives, we aspire to advance pharmaceutical technology and contribute to a greener, more sustainable future in healthcare.

Life as an MSCA Fellow

The first few months as an MSCA Fellow have been filled with enriching activities and experiences. We kicked off the program with an online meeting in March, where each fellow introduced themselves and presented their research project. A few months later, we were able to meet in person for a fruitful soft skills training session at MyBiotech GmbH in Germany.

More recently, we attended our first international meeting and summer school at the University of Trieste in Italy. This event provided an invaluable opportunity to share our initial research results with peers and supervisors while also gaining insights into biopolymer degradation and characterization. Meeting people from so many diverse backgrounds and experiences has been incredibly rewarding, and I am excited about what lies ahead.

Moreover, I have been actively working on my research project, which I conduct jointly between Nanomol Technologies and ICMAB-CSIC. Both institutions are conveniently located on the Autonomous University of Barcelona (UAB) campus, just a short walk from each other. Currently, I carry out most of my experiments at Nanomol Technologies, while my weekly visits to ICMAB-CSIC allow me to attend group seminars and access specialized equipment.

Team building at Nanomol Technologies (Escape room in Barcelona)

[LinkedIn](#)

Nov 2024

Nicolas

who I am?

Hi, my name is Nicolas. I'm 26 years old and originally from France. I was born in Marseille and later moved to Paris. I studied the fundamentals of engineering and went on to attend the Paris School of Chemistry, Chimie ParisTech-PSL. I graduated with a Master's degree in Integrative Chemistry. I've always been enthusiast about experimental science. Currently, I am pursuing my PhD in Barcelona, Spain. My research is done jointly between the Institute of Materials Science of Barcelona and the start-up company Nanomol Technology SL.

My Project

To combat this issue, I focus on the design of advanced nanoparticles with inherent antimicrobial properties. These nanoparticles can be precisely loaded with one or more types of actives using DELOS (Depressurization of an Ex-panded Liquid Organic Solution)- a green, CO₂-based, one-step and scalable manufacturing process. Specifically, my work aims to develop nanoformulations containing Antimicrobial Peptides (AMPs). AMPs are effective against pathogens and less prone to resistance, offering potential to enhance antimicrobial formulations. Additionally, I will explore strategies for opening up applications beyond pharmaceuticals, such as antimicrobial packaging materials. The goal is to create stable, efficient formulations suitable for clinical use, addressing current and emerging medical needs.

Additionally, I assessed its *in-vitro* antimicrobial activity against various microorganisms.

Update on My PhD journey

Since I arrived in Barcelona in 9 months ago, the project has been a very rich experience.

I've been delighted by the friendly atmosphere, as well as the excellent work environment and infrastructure.

Outside of work, I joined a sailing club and enjoyed exploring what Barcelona has to offer.

Meeting with the GreenX3 consortium in Germany and Trieste was a great opportunity to develop transversal skills and gain new perspectives on my daily work by exchanging with people in the same situation as me. It was also the opportunity to build great friendships that I'm looking forward to continue!

My Advancement

To date, my work has focused on developing a specific combination of an AMP and a nanocarrier. I successfully synthesized the nanoconjugate, and achieve effective drug encapsulation. I have evaluated key physicochemical properties, such as morphology, size, and homogeneity.

Sara Spada

Hello everyone!

My name is Sara, and I am a first-year MSCA doctoral candidate currently based at GEC laboratory at Université de Technologie de Compiègne (UTC) in France!

Thesis Project

My research project focuses on developing molecularly imprinted polymers (MIPs) for specific and selective capture of biological molecules. Getting inspired by biological recognition process (e.g. antibody-antigen recognition), I rely on molecular imprinting technology to synthesize these polymers with specific binding sites.

As part of this *GreenX3* network, I'll look into greener materials, by exploiting bio-sourced and/or biodegradable materials that can be used to produce MIP to ensure a better eco- and bio-compatibility.

Life as a MSCA PhD Fellow

Since our last newsletter we had our First international meeting and summer school in Trieste!

Fête de la Science

This past October we took part to the 33rd Fête de la Science! Fête de la Science is an important outreach event here in France which aims to bring together the scientific world and the great public. Within this event we had the opportunity to present our lab, our research and techniques to a great public: school classes, kids with their families, and all people passionate of science. Theme of our stand was "Le plastique, fantastique?" By exposing our research and work, we invited people to answer and draw their own conclusions to this provocative question.

...and Kyra and I started our project with our industrial partner, Protera! Here a picture of our first day in Protera with Laure and Mathilda!

Picture of the stand at Fête de la Science

Our journey started by explaining molecular imprinting technique and how synthetic antibodies -known as MIPs- can be engineered to possess thermo-responsive properties. Moving on, an interactive game was set to get people aware of how long it takes to degrade different plastic derivatives commonly used in everyday life. To conclude, we presented possible bio-based products (e.g. alginate or chitosan) that can be exploited in research to replace petrol-based derivatives.

It was an amazing opportunity of scientific communication to the great public, and I was very enthusiastic to be part of this amazing event!

Kyra Magdato

Bonjour! I am Kyra from the Philippines, currently based in the Génie enzymatique et cellulaire of UTC in Compiègne, France and doing my industrial secondment at Protera. My research interests revolve around polymer chemistry, and materials science. I obtained my bachelor's and master's degree in chemistry from the University of the Philippines Diliman. Since the last newsletter, PhD life has been quite an interesting experience. In this newsletter, I am sharing some photos and stories of what has transpired within the past nine months.

Thesis Project

The main goal of my project is the development of smart encapsulation and packaging materials. Smart packaging materials is an emerging field as a response to changes in the demand of consumers and to mitigate the environmental consequences brought about by using packaging materials fabricated from non-renewable resources. For the first year, we focus on the fabrication of a sensor that can be incorporated to packaging materials for the non-invasive monitoring and recognition of target molecules by employing molecular imprinting technology. I also started my industrial secondment at Protera and I am looking forward to share this experience soon.

Snaps from our 1st Summer School in Trieste, Italy

MSCA DC Experience

With our first meeting in MyBiotech, Germany in June and the summer school in Trieste, I was able to meet my fellow DCs and it was a memorable and enriching experience to share with all of them. It was a chance for us to share stories about our PhD lives fostering new friendships and great connections.

Fête de la Science

Fête de la Science is an annual event in France to promote science and technology through exhibits and booths allowing interactions and discourse between scientists and the public, from toddlers to adults. This year's theme is "Ocean of Knowledge" revolving around climate regulation, functioning of oceans, ecosystems, and human development.

This year, GEC, where I am based, prepared a booth entitled "Le plastique, fantastique?" showing the concept of molecular imprinting with interactive models for kids and bio-sourced materials like chitosan films and alginate beads as innovative and greener alternatives for packaging and encapsulation materials.

As a PhD fellow in the GreenX3 network, this was an opportunity for me to communicate my science to other people, not solely on a technical approach, but also more on the environmental and societal significance of our research. Moreover, it is also a fulfilling experience to see how young kids are amazed with science and hopefully inspire them to pursue a career in science.

Akshay Ranganath

Hi everyone, welcome back to my page. Reintroducing again, this is Akshay Ranganath (DC-9) from Mysuru (India) and I am here in Trieste (Italy) conducting research at University of Trieste. A scholarly area, Trieste has the highest percentage of researchers, per capita, in Europe. *Città della bora* ("City of the bora"), *Città del vento* ("City of Wind"), "Vienna by the sea" and "City of Coffee" are epithets used to describe Trieste. The stupendous celebration of "Barcolana" festival has always stood the test of time and on being passed by the pleasant Barcola beach always greets with a whoop of delight.

Elettra – Sincrotrone Trieste has been the coordinator of the EU-supported networks involving synchrotron and free electron lasers in the European area, in the last decade.. The facility, available for use by the Italian and international scientific communities, houses several ultra bright light sources, which use the synchrotron and free electron laser (FEL) sources to produce light ranging from ultraviolet to X-rays.

Need for organic decaffeination process & my research objectives.

The deleterious effects of excessive caffeine consumption are only partially understood at present. However, what is known is sufficient to generally determine and conclude that caffeine is potentially detrimental when consumed in excess. Decaffeinated coffees have long been on the market. However, there are a few significant problems inherent with currently known decaffeination processes. The efficacy of current decaffeination methods varies considerably with the method. While some are capable of removing substantial percentages of caffeine, other methods are not as effective.

From the environmental perspective a process for decaffeinating aqueous solutions that conserves energy and substantially lessens the use of organic solvents is desirable.

The main objectives of our project not only includes the exploitation of natural organic materials and reactants to build a polymeric adsorbent for caffeine removal but also to develop an aqueous medium optimized for active ingredients and coffee aromas. Nevertheless, recovery of caffeine from capturing materials is an additional goal to prevent consistent loss of caffeine during recycling process.

Industrial secondments & scientific Progress

I was immediately seconded at Demus (SPA) soon after my arrival in Trieste and still couldn't forget the gracious welcoming offered by our beloved Professors. My industrial secondments were commenced under the benevolent supervision of Doctor Desobgo, who galvanized me with his shrewd competencies of coffee researches. During my days at DEMUS I was trained to operate the most inquisitive pilot plant, small scale decaf setup, coffee roasters, brewers and on developing organoleptic skills. Nonetheless, in order to fulfil my preliminary objective to develop an aqueous media optimized for novel materials I exploited few of the natural ingredients as additives to enhance the decaffeination by preventing weight loss of the coffee beans. In between my secondments an opportunity to visit Germany fell on my lap as Greenx3 organized a training on soft skills & team building activities at MyBiotech GmbH company. International meeting & yearly summer school organized at Trieste were truly essential assets for all of us. As far as I'm concerned, I am exploring highly valuable prerogative skills & activities under GreenX3 project and hoping a lucrative career indeed.

GreenX3-DC10

Supervisor: Prof. Cristina Forzato
The University of Trieste – Demus, Italy

Getting to know me :) from my hometown to Trieste

Hi there! I'm Mandana, a first-year doctoral candidate in the *GreenX3* project. Six months ago, I left my hometown and embarked on an exciting new chapter at the University of Trieste in northeast Italy which is surrounded by the sea and lush green mountains, Trieste welcomed me with open arms, reminding me so much of home. Another reason I have settled in so well here is my adorable supervisors and the amazing friends I have made in the lab. Their kindness, support, and camaraderie make every day enjoyable. Whether we are discussing experiments or simply sharing a laugh, they have turned the lab into a second home for me, and I couldn't be happier.

Co-supervisor: Prof. Federico Berti
Industrial Co-supervisor: Dr. Yves Clyford Desobgo

UNIVERSITÀ
DEGLI STUDI
DI TRIESTE

My Objective: providing you with a better cup of decaf coffee

Let me take you to the heart of my work, coffee! So delicious! My project dives into the world of decaffeination, with the goal of making it greener and more efficient. Decaf coffee has all the flavor and health benefits of regular coffee, like reducing risks of diabetes and dementia, without the side effects of caffeine. But here's the catch: the current methods to remove caffeine come with environmental and health challenges, including high water use, chemical instability, and the release of harmful arsenic. That's where I come in. My mission? To reimagine the decaffeination process using sustainable techniques. I'm exploring ways to capture arsenic, reduce water consumption, and improve the process's stability and efficiency. Imagine a future where your morning cup of decaf coffee is not only delicious but also a win for the planet! To make this happen, I'm developing and testing novel compounds derived from natural molecules. These materials will not only help recover caffeine but will also ensure the final product meets strict organic food standards. My work doesn't stop in the lab; soon, I will take these ideas to an industrial scale at Demus, a company dedicated to coffee innovation.

Joining a global family with green mission

Being part of the *GreenX3* project is more than just research, it is like joining a global family. Together, we aim to revolutionize the way materials and processes are used, creating a circular economy that is kind to the planet. The project's focus on greener materials and their environmental impact resonates deeply with me. It is about making a difference, creating solutions that benefit not just us but generations to come. I will never forget the moment I met my fellow *GreenX3* candidates in Germany for the first time. Coming from all corners of the world, we shared laughter, ideas, and dreams. I felt like I was walking on air, knowing I was part of something so impactful. Every conversation with my peers broadens my perspective, reminding me of the beauty in diversity and collaboration.

My lab, My playground

In the meantime, my lab in Trieste has become my creative playground. Here, I have built a small pilot plant to replicate the decaffeination process. Every day feels like an adventure as I experiment with different conditions and materials to find the best solutions. For example, I have been comparing the caffeine concentrations in decaffeinated coffee beans and different types of chlorogenic acids to evaluate how selective our filter can be. I have also been measuring arsenic levels in decaffeinated coffee beans to understand its sources and reduce its impact. Beyond that, I am exploring ways to modify waste materials to remove arsenic and extend the shelf life of the solvent syrup used in the process. Each discovery feels like a puzzle piece falling into place. I will transition to the industrial phase of my research, where my lab work will come to life on a larger scale. It is exciting to imagine how my efforts might one day change the way we think about sustainability and coffee.

Stay tuned, this is only the beginning :)

Who is Megan, aka DNS11?

Hello! My name is Megan Gutman, and I am a Doctoral Network Candidate at Queen Mary University of London (QMUL). I obtained my B.Sc. in Chemistry from the University of Michigan (U-M), and my M.Sc in Chemistry from the Technical University of Munich (TUM). I'm passionate about key emerging technologies in green chemistry, which compliment my research interests in polymer and material science. When I'm not in the lab, you'll find me experimenting in the kitchen, traveling, or sweating at a HIIT class.

International Meeting – Trieste, Italy

Getting Industrial!

Over the past few months, I have been integrating into a new work environment during my industrial placement at Symphony Environmental Ltd (SEL). This partnership is key to my project, which focuses on how littered plastics degrade and interact with natural materials. Plastics take a long time to break down, leading to accumulation in the environment. Given the time constraints of a PhD project, accelerated ageing methods are essential to replicate natural weathering. By collaborating with SEL, we utilize their fast-degrading plastic formulations and accelerated ageing chambers to simulate environmental stressors. This approach enables us to assess the degradation behavior of various materials that threaten ecosystems and, most recently, human health via microplastics.

To address these challenges, my objectives are to:

- 1) Develop accelerated artificial ageing and weathering protocols
- 2) Analyze the ageing behavior of commodity plastics using advanced techniques
- 3) Evaluate new plastic formulations, such as "biodegradable" alternatives
- 4) Investigate the interactions between biological materials and aged plastics.

Playing with Plastics

Have you ever wondered where your plastic grocery bag comes from? Since starting my industrial placement at Symphony Environmental Ltd., I've shifted my polymer science background to practice. To have strict control over the materials I'm testing, we have prepared the plastic formulations ourselves, compounding our formulations on a twin-screw extruder, and then sending them through the same device which makes plastic bags. This device essentially melts the plastic, pushes it through a circular hole, and blows a fast stream of air through the center to keep a tubular shape while it cools... tubular!

These are the film samples I evaluate during our accelerated ageing tests, where lamps replicate portions of the sun's radiation which age plastics, and heat is applied, which speeds up the ageing process.

After that, we evaluate the new surface chemistry that this process generates and quantify it using analytical devices and programs.

Ever notice how an old rubber band gets cracks and breaks easily when stretched? We want to evaluate this kind of behavior as well in the next steps of my project, as it may be a good predictive marker of microplastic formation.

Eda Duranay

Greetings, readers! I'm Eda, currently in London as a Doctoral Network Student at Queen Mary University of London (QMUL). Before settling in this vibrant city, I lived in İzmir, Ankara, and Munich for my studies. Besides my academic pursuits, I'm passionate about exploring new destinations, immersing myself in the arts, and staying active with hobbies like ballroom dancing, yoga, and kayaking. These activities provide me with a sense of fulfillment and balance in life.

Tackling Plastic Pollution: My Journey at Notpla

I am currently undertaking an industrial secondment at Notpla, an innovative London-based company at the forefront of sustainable packaging solutions. Notpla aims to tackle one of our most pressing environmental challenges: single-use plastic pollution. By harnessing the power of seaweed and other renewable natural materials, the company develops cutting-edge, biodegradable packaging alternatives. My work involves analyzing how varying formulations and processing conditions influence the properties and performance of the films, ensuring they meet the desired criteria for strength, flexibility, and biodegradability. Additionally, I am investigating the effects of UV exposure, heat, humidity, and time on the films to understand their shelf-life and practicality in real-world applications. To further quantify the environmental benefits of Notpla's products, I am conducting comparative studies to evaluate the biodegradability of these films against conventional bioplastics such as PLA (polylactic acid) and PVA (polyvinyl alcohol).

Baking Science: Turning Plastic Pollution into a Sweet Lesson

Apart from my industrial and research activities, I participated in the "Bake a PhD" competition at my home institution, Queen Mary University of London. I baked a cake to creatively highlight the issue of plastic pollution. It was a small but impactful way to connect with people and start conversations about sustainability.

Building Bridges Across Europe

The GreenX3 network is as much about collaboration as it is about science. Meeting doctoral candidates from across Europe has been an enriching experience, especially during events in Überherrn and Trieste. Beyond exchanging ideas and sharing knowledge, there were moments of connection. These experiences remind us that while tackling global challenges is serious work, the relationships built along the way are just as important.

Supervisor: Prof. Marina Resmini

Supervisor: Dr. Erinc Bahcegul

Summer school, Trieste

Timpy

Hi, I'm Timpy from India. I graduated in Analytical Chemistry from the University of Delhi in 2021, and my passion for addressing environmental issues led me to the Erasmus Mundus Master's in Environmental Contamination and Toxicology. This program allowed me to study at universities in France, Norway, Spain and Switzerland. I'm enthusiastic to using my chemistry skills to tackle environmental challenges. In my free time, I enjoy hiking, cooking, exploring, celebrating cultures, and learning swimming, yoga, photography and salsa.

Greener materials and their environmental impact

Plastic pollution
(The Ocean Cleanup)

Focus: Microbiology & ecotoxicology

- Meet biodegradability standards for packaging
- Apply biodegradability tests in industry
- Compare to oil-based materials

Deliverables

- D1.1 Chemical degradation – artificial weathering
- D1.2 Characterization of degraded samples
- D1.3 Biodegradability by microbiology
- D1.4 Ecotoxicology with *Capitella teleta*
- D1.5 Translation of biodegradability assays into industrial settings

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My first industrial experience ! Exciting world of worms

As part of my Industrial PhD, I recently started my placement at Notpla Ltd. and have been immersing myself in a new work environment over the past few months.

What makes Notpla unique is their commitment to sustainable innovation: they create materials from seaweed, offering a convenient solution that doesn't harm the planet. Unlike single-use plastics, seaweed is an exceptional resource as it requires no land, freshwater, or fertilizers and is abundantly available.

Since these materials are relatively new, there's limited knowledge about their biodegradability and ecotoxicity—this is where my role becomes essential.

Currently, my objectives include:

- Characterizing coatings to assess the effects of plasticizers
- Studying shelf life and the impacts of UV exposure, heat, humidity, and time
- Conducting ecotoxicity experiments with *Capitella teleta*

As part of my PhD work, I recently began studying *Capitella teleta*, a cosmopolitan worm that thrives in organic marine sediments and is easy to culture in the lab. I am excited to investigate the ecotoxicity of Notpla's materials on *Capitella teleta* and contribute valuable insights into their environmental impact. Below are some pictures of me working, a female *Capitella teleta*, a brood, and larvae.

Past Events

PI Kick-Off Meeting
29.09.2023 | [Online](#)

DC Kick-Off Meeting
26.03.2024 | [Online](#)

Training on Team Building & Soft Skills
04.06. -05.06.2024 | [FMI](#)
MyBiotech, Überherrn – Germany

1st International Meeting
09.09. - 10.09.2024 | UNITS,
Trieste - Italy

1st Summer School –
Towards Green Materials
11.09 - 13.09.2024 | UNITS,
Trieste - Italy

Upcoming Events

1st Workshop – The power
of virtual reality
13.01 – 14.01.2024 | Online

Thank you for reading!

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